

The Reaction Pathways for HSCH₃ Adsorption on Au(111): A Density Functional Theory Study

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Density functional theory was used to investigate the reaction pathways for HSCH₃ adsorption on Au(111) at low coverage. A molecular adsorbed state was found with the S atom bond on Top sites ($E \sim -0.38$ eV) and molecular adsorption is nonactivated. The H–SCH₃ dissociation process is energetically less favorable and becomes slightly exothermic only when surface relaxation is considered ($\Delta E \sim -0.2$ eV). All the reaction pathways present a sizable activation energy barrier, with the lowest being ~ 0.52 eV (0.41 eV taking into account slab relaxation). In the corresponding saddle point of the potential energy surface, the S atom of the methylthiolate molecule is placed on Top sites and the H near a Bridge site. The high barrier obtained explains the complete absence of reactive methanethiol dissociation found in recent experiments.

I. Introduction

Gold surfaces and anchor sulfur organic groups such as alkanethiols [HS(CH₂) _{$n-1$} CH₃] and disulfides (RSSR, with R representing an alkyl chain) are the prototype components of supramolecular systems using self-assembled monolayers (SAMs)¹ for the functionalization of extended surfaces and for the preparation of monolayer *protected* clusters. Given the wealth of potential technological applications, including corrosion inhibition, lithography, lubrication, catalysis, and molecular recognition, the interest in the underlying chemistry and physics of such systems has been steadily growing during recent years (see refs 1–5 and references therein).

In the case of alkanethiols on gold surfaces, it is usually assumed that stable SAMs involve thiolate radicals (after the H–S bond cleavage), but in general, neither how these radicals are produced nor the fate of the liberated H atoms is clearly understood. Even in the simplest scenario of ultrahigh-vacuum (UHV) conditions and well-characterized surfaces, many fundamental aspects of the initial thiol adsorption process (the first and maybe the simplest step in SAMs formation) are still under discussion: (i) the chemical or physical nature of the molecule-surface bonding (chemisorption vs physisorption), (ii) the conditions for molecular or dissociative adsorption, possible mechanisms for the H–S bond cleavage and the role of coverage, Θ , (iii) the adsorption site and the orientation of the alkyl chain of the thiolate radical, and (iv) the precise influence of the alkyl chain length.

Although stable SAMs are usually made of long alkyl chains ($n \sim 6-11$), the difficult theoretical treatment of such complex molecules is the reason why short-chain thiols (typically HSCH₃) are widely employed as model systems. Most of these studies,

based on density functional theory (DFT) calculations,^{6,7} have been focused on the adsorption site and orientation of SCH₃ on Au(111).⁸⁻¹³ The chemisorption energy predicted by DFT for methylthiolate on Au(111) (e.g., ~ 1.7 eV¹⁰) is in good agreement with the experimental value, i.e., 1.73 eV.² The most recent DFT calculations indicate that the most favorable region for the adsorption of SCH₃ is around the Bridge-Fcc site (located between the Bridge and Hollow-Fcc sites).^{9,11-14} This was first supported by high-resolution electron energy loss spectroscopy (HREELS) experiments,⁹ but later, results of photoelectron diffraction¹⁵ and normal incidence X-ray standing wave techniques¹⁶ pointed to the Top site as the most stable site for chemisorption of SCH₃ on Au(111), at odds with the DFT prediction. Very recently, Maksymovych et al. concluded, from a combined scanning tunneling microscopy/DFT study, that the S-headgroup of chemisorbed SCH₃ adsorbs around the twofold coordinated Bridge site between two Au atoms.¹⁷

The energetics and geometry of the molecular (nondissociated) adsorbed state of HSCH₃ on Au(111) have also been investigated.^{8,11,13,18} The DFT adsorption energies^{8,13,18} are in reasonably good agreement with the experimental value (~ 0.5 eV¹⁹), with discrepancies being lower than ~ 0.15 eV (the typical error of state-of-the-art electronic surface structure calculations). More-

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over, both DFT calculations and experiments^{8,11,13,18} indicate the Top site as the most stable for molecular adsorption.

The global energetics of possible reactions that produce SCH₃ radicals on Au(111) from H-SCH₃ (methanethiol) and H₃CS-SCH₃ (dimethyl disulfide) have been much less investigated. Some authors found that the dissociative adsorption process

on Au(111) is exothermic,^{8,20} whereas other studies indicate that it is slightly endothermic.¹⁰

An alternative mechanism involving two HSCH₃ molecules and the formation and desorption of an H₂ molecule has also been invoked.^{2,10,20} This process, usually called the hydrogen channel, is energetically more favorable than eq 1 because of the exothermicity of the H₂ desorption process. However, this mechanism might only become relevant at high coverage and below the desorption temperature of the molecular state ($T_s \sim 150\text{--}200\text{ K}$ ²²), because two adsorbed molecules close to each other are required for this mechanism to take place.

Nuzzo and co-workers²¹ estimated a very small value of the reactive sticking coefficient of HSCH₃ on Au(111) ($\sim 10^{-5}$ at 300 K). Recently, Yates et al.²² found no evidence of S-H (or C-S) bond cleavage during the adsorption of HSCH₃ and DSCH₃ on Au(111) using temperature-programmed desorption (TPD), Auger electron spectroscopy (AES), and low-temperature scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) experiments. The existence of an activation energy barrier of $\sim 0.3\text{ eV}$ has been proposed²¹ to explain such a small dissociative adsorption probability. However, a detailed theoretical study aimed at determining the most favorable dissociation pathway and the associated activation energy is still lacking. To our knowledge, only Sellers²⁰ estimated an activation energy of 0.18 eV relative to the gas-phase reactants using the bond order conservation-Morse potential (BOC-MP) model.^{23,24} This absence of detailed theoretical studies is certainly due to the extremely complex potential energy surface (PES) of HSCH₃/Au(111), which makes the search of possible dissociation pathways computationally very demanding.

In this paper, we investigate some possible reaction pathways for H-SCH₃ bond cleavage on a clean, defect-free Au(111) surface to understand the origin of the small reactive sticking probability observed in experiments. In section II, we briefly describe the details of the computational method employed. In section III, we present the energies and most stable geometries for the molecular and dissociative adsorbed states of HSCH₃. Then, we investigate some possible H-SCH₃ dissociation pathways and provide an estimation of the corresponding minimum activation barrier for a frozen substrate as well as taking into account adsorbate-induced surface relaxation. The main conclusions of our study are summarized in section IV.

II. Computational Details

The DFT calculations described in this paper have been carried out within the slab-supercell approach²⁵ by using the Vienna ab initio simulation program (VASP).^{26–29} The one-electron Kohn–

Sham orbitals are expanded in a plane wave basis set and electron–ion interactions are described through the ultrasoft pseudopotentials (USSPs)³⁰ obtained by Kresse and Hafner.³¹ Exchange and correlation (XC) is described within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) introduced by Perdew and Wang (PW91),³² which performs well for the global energetics of several reactions involving sulfur-containing molecules (including HSCH₃) on Au(111).¹⁰ The sampling of the Brillouin zone is carried out according to the Monkhorst–Pack method.³³ Electron smearing was introduced following the Methfessel–Paxton technique³⁴ with $\sigma = 0.2\text{ eV}$, and all the energies are extrapolated to 0 K. The cutoff energy is 350 eV, and the calculations are spin-restricted.

The theoretical lattice constant obtained for the Au bulk (using a $9 \times 9 \times 9$ k -point mesh) is $a_{\text{calc}} = 4.185\text{ \AA}$, in good agreement with the experimental value, $a_{\text{exp}} = 4.078\text{ \AA}$. To represent the Au(111) surface, we use a three-layer slab, and no significant relaxation of the interlayer distance with respect to the bulk value is observed. Previous DFT results¹⁰ indicate that three Au layers are enough to obtain well-converged values of adsorption energies on Au(111). The vacuum region between consecutive slabs is $\sim 24\text{ \AA}$ thick. To study the adsorption energetics at low coverage, we have carried out calculations for a single HSCH₃ molecule within a 3×3 supercell. A few calculations for a ($\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$)R30° cell will be also presented to illustrate possible coverage effects. The results for the 3×3 ($\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$) supercell were obtained using a $3 \times 3 \times 1$ ($7 \times 7 \times 1$) k -point mesh. Although it is well-known that Au(111) presents a $22 \times \sqrt{3}$ reconstructed structure, it is assumed that this does not play an important role in the dissociation of HSCH₃ molecules.

The obtained equilibrium geometry of the HSCH₃ molecule in a vacuum is in excellent agreement with the experimental one:³⁵ the bond lengths are $d_{\text{H-S}} = 1.348\text{ \AA}$ ($d_{\text{H-S}}^{\text{exp}} = 1.340\text{ \AA}$), $d_{\text{S-C}} = 1.781\text{ \AA}$ ($d_{\text{S-C}}^{\text{exp}} = 1.819\text{ \AA}$), $d_{\text{C-H}} = 1.088\text{ \AA}$ ($d_{\text{C-H}}^{\text{exp}} = 1.090\text{ \AA}$), and the angle $\varphi(\text{C-S-H}) = 97.06^\circ$ ($\varphi_{\text{exp}}(\text{C-S-H}) = 96.5^\circ$). Throughout this paper, we define the reference energy level $E = 0$ as the energy of the equilibrium geometry of the HSCH₃ molecule in the middle of the vacuum space (i.e., the energy of the *reactants* for the adsorption process), and the adsorption sites of HSCH₃ and SCH₃ are identified by the position of the S atom on the surface.

III. Results and Discussions

The existence of a weakly bound molecular adsorbed state for alkanethiols of different chain lengths on Au(111) is well-established. Moreover, it is often assumed that this state is a precursor for the H-S bond cleavage reaction. Therefore, we first investigated the molecular adsorption process (section III.A), and then, in section III.B we present the energies and geometries of different possible dissociated states. Finally, in section III.C we investigated possible reaction pathways and the corresponding activation energy barriers for the H-SCH₃ bond cleavage process by using a combination of nudged elastic band (NEB)^{36–38} and adaptive NEB (ANEBA) methods.³⁹

A. Molecular Adsorption (MAS). The HSCH₃ molecule was initially placed near the surface on several high- and low-symmetry sites, with the plane containing the H-S-C bonds parallel and perpendicular to the surface, i.e., lying down and

Table 1. Molecular Adsorption Energy of HSCH₃/Au(111) for a 3 × 3 and (√3 × √3)R30° Supercells^a

supercell	adsorption site	Θ	d_{S-Au} (Å)	d_{H-Au} (Å)	α_{S-C} (°)	E (eV)
3 × 3	Hollow	1/9	3.95	3.12	81	-0.12
	Bridge	1/9	3.83	3.46	89	-0.13
	Top	1/9	2.58	3.02	69	-0.35
	Top'	1/9	2.65	3.08	69	-0.38
(√3 × √3)R30°	Top	1/3	3.00	3.07	72	-0.13
	Hollow-fcc	1/3	3.77	2.84	75	-0.06
	Hollow-hcp	1/3	3.75	2.80	82	-0.08

^a d_{X-Y} indicates the distance between the nearest X and Y atoms and α_{S-C} is the angle between the S-C bond and the surface normal.

Figure 1. Molecular adsorbed state (MAS): (a) Top and (b) side views. The S atom is on Top' (see the text), the C atom is close to a Hollow-Hcp site, and the H atom bound to S is near a Bridge site. The lower panel corresponds to the Top view of configuration α ; see text.

upright configurations, respectively. Then, we carried out geometry optimization of the molecular degrees of freedom, keeping fixed the initial adsorption site of the S atom. A summary of our results is presented in Table 1. The energetically most stable states were always found for the initially lying down molecular configurations. The lowest energy was obtained for the HSCH₃ molecule with S on Top, and the angle between the S-C bond and the surface normal is $\alpha_{S-C} = 69^\circ$. Full geometry optimization starting from the latter geometry gives rise to the most stable molecular adsorbed state (MAS) shown in Figure 1a.

The adsorption energy of the MAS is -0.38 eV and the distance between the S atom and its nearest Au atom is $d_{S-Au} = 2.65$ Å (see Figure 1b). For this state, we have checked that dipole corrections^{40,41} do not modify this adsorption energy. In the MAS, the S atom is bound on a surface site very close to Top (referred to as Top' in Table 1), the C atom is close to a Hollow-Hcp site, and the H atom bound to S is near to Bridge site (see Figure 1a). DFT calculations also predict that HSCH₃ molecularly adsorbed on Au(111) can rotate almost freely around top sites. For instance, the energy of configuration α (Figure 1c), characterized by an angle between S-H and Au-Au bonds of 30° , is almost the

Figure 2. Dissociated state (DS): (a) Top and (b) side views of the most stable DS (see the text). The S atom is on a Bridge-Fcc site with the surface projected S-C bond pointing to Hollow-Hcp site, and the H on a Hollow-Fcc site (position A in the text). The B, C, and D positions correspond to different H location considered for others energies evaluations. In (b) is shown the d_{S-Au} distance. The lower panel corresponds to the Top view of configuration β , with the S atom located on Bridge-Hcp.

same as that of the MAS. This behavior has been confirmed by low surface temperature STM images.¹⁸ Our DFT results summarized above are in good agreement with previous theoretical results^{13,18} and estimations from experiments carried out by Nuzzo and co-workers.²¹ It is also important to mention that our DFT results predict that molecular adsorption is a nonactivated process, which is consistent with the large sticking probability obtained in experiments carried out by exposing a cold ($T_s \sim 77$ K) Au(111) surface to thermally excited HSCH₃ molecules.

In Table 1, we have also included results for a $(\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3})R30^\circ$ supercell ($\Theta = 1/3$). For this higher coverage, the Top site is also the most stable for molecular adsorption. However, the corresponding adsorption energy is smaller than for the 3×3 cell by 0.25 eV. This is consistent with recent TPD experiments which showed that the desorption temperature from the molecular state decreases when the surface coverage increases (see Figure 1 of ref 22).

B. Dissociated States (DS). The HSCH₃ molecule can be considered dissociated when the H atom and the SCH₃ group are both chemisorbed in stable configurations (local minima of the PES) and far from each other. Starting from several high- and low-symmetry sites, we performed full geometry optimization of the H atom and the SCH₃ group (simultaneously) within the 3×3 supercell. The energy of the most stable DS that we have found is $+0.01$ eV. The chemisorption geometry of this state is shown in Figure 2 (panels a and b).

The SCH₃ group preferentially chemisorbs with the S atom on Bridge-Fcc sites ($d_{S-Au} = 2.52$ Å), the surface-projected S-C bond pointing to a Hollow-Hcp site, and $\alpha_{S-C} = 56.3^\circ$. Very similar adsorption geometries have been obtained in previous DFT studies,^{10,12,13,17} and recent STM images obtained at low surface temperatures and low coverage¹⁷ seem to confirm this theoretical prediction. As in the case of clean Au(111), the H atom chemisorbs on Hollow-Fcc sites (see Figure 3), with adsorption on Hollow-Hcp being less stable by only a few millielectronvolts. The chemisorption energy of a DS slightly depends on the distance between the H atom and the SCH₃ group. For instance, if the position of the SCH₃ group is kept fixed, the energies of the DS with the H atom on the Hollow-Fcc sites

Figure 3. Potential energy for H on Au(111) as a function of the H–Au topmost layer distance, Z . \bullet —, Top site; \circ —, Bridge site; \diamond —, Hollow fcc site. Reported energies are relative to the value for an H atom far (~ 12 Å) from the surface obtained in a spin-unrestricted calculation.

labeled with B and C (Figure 2a) are $+0.08$ eV and $+0.04$ eV, respectively, whereas full geometry optimization starting with the H atom on the Hollow-Hcp site D ends in the configuration depicted in Figure 2a, the most stable DS.

The change of the SCH_3 adsorption site from Bridge-Fcc to Bridge-Hcp also entails a relatively small energy variation. For instance, the energy of the DS shown in Figure 2c (hereafter referred to as β configuration) is $+0.09$ eV.

Taking into account the most stable DS we have found, reactants and products are almost energetically degenerate ($\Delta E = +0.01$ eV). This value lies between previous results of Gottschalck and Hammer¹⁰ and Zhou and Hagelberg⁴² who found, respectively, $\Delta E = +0.12$ eV and $\Delta E = -0.06$ eV (in GGA-PW91 calculations). In contrast, our results disagree with those of Gronbeck et al. who found that H– SCH_3 dissociation is exothermic, with $\Delta E = -0.70$ eV and $\Delta E = -0.47$ eV, in GGA-PBE and BLYP calculations, respectively.⁸

From the global energetics, we have found for $\text{HSCH}_3/\text{Au}(111)$ that molecular adsorption ($\Delta E = -0.38$ eV) is energetically more favorable than H– SCH_3 dissociation ($\Delta E = +0.01$ eV or -0.18 eV if surface relaxation is considered; see below). This is not sufficient to explain the complete absence of H–S dissociation resulting from the TPD experiments of Maksymovych et al.¹⁸ Low-energy molecules might temporarily dissociate and then recombine to desorb as a thiol molecule. However, the absence of any change in the isotopomer ratio in desorbing molecules after dosing Au(111) with a 50:50 mixture of DSCH_3 and HSCH_3 molecules excludes this possibility. This points to the existence of an energetic activation barrier for the H–S bond breaking process. This is certainly a motivation to look for the most favorable dissociation pathway (MFDP) and the corresponding activation energy barrier. Moreover, we hope the characteristics of the MFDP for H– SCH_3 might provide some guidance for future studies of long-chain alkanethiol dissociation, which becomes spontaneous for more than $n \approx 6$ C atoms.

C. Reaction Pathways. We have used the nudged elastic band (NEB)^{36–38} method to search possible H– SCH_3 dissociation pathways. The NEB method has been widely employed to determine minimum-energy pathways and activation energy barriers for many gas-phase and surface reactions. The high dimensionality of the HSCH_3 -Au(111) PES (18 neglecting surface

Figure 4. Investigated reaction pathways. The arrows indicate the motion of the H and S atoms. The initial and final states for pathways I are the MAS state and the configuration β , and for pathway II are configuration α and the DS state.

degrees of freedom) makes this search computationally extremely demanding. Therefore, we have used a combination of the standard NEB method with the ANEBA algorithm proposed by Maragakis et al. in order to reduce the computational cost of the calculations.³⁹ When using these methods, one first has to choose the initial and final states of the process of interest as well as an initial guess of intermediate states.

We have investigated reaction pathways starting from the MAS and the configuration α displayed in Figure 1, with the dissociating H atom respectively moving first toward the nearest Top and Bridge sites, and then, both H and the SCH_3 group going to their positions in the closest stable DS. This gives rise to the initial guess of reaction pathways I and II shown in Figure 4 for which the final states are the DS displayed in Figure 2a,c, respectively.

For pathways I and II, we have first carried out 150 steps of the standard NEB method with 7 movable intermediate images. Then, we applied the iterative ANEBA method.³⁹ The results of this procedure for pathways I and II are presented in the top panels of Figure 5. In each level of the ANEBA method, the 2 images adjacent to the one with the highest energy along the path obtained in the previous step are chosen as the initial and final configurations for a new three-movable-image NEB calculation. In the first levels, typically more than 100 iterations of NEB were carried out until the forces perpendicular to the reaction path were considerably small. In the higher levels of ANEBA, convergence of the NEB method (that requires a change in the total energy of the *chain* with respect to the previous step of less than 0.1 meV) was reached after only a few iterations. For pathways I and II, we stopped this iterative procedure, respectively, after 5 and 4 levels of ANEBA, obtaining activation energy barriers of 0.56 and 0.52 eV (see upper panels of Figure 5).

To verify that the points of highest energy of the two pathways are saddle points, we first relaxed the 18 coordinates of the molecule, for each of its 2 adjacent images in the last ANEBA level. We checked that one relaxes to the molecular adsorbed state and the other goes to the dissociated state. Afterward, we relaxed all the coordinates of the candidate to the transition state, and no significant modifications of the geometrical configuration of the molecule were found. Finally, we performed a Hessian matrix calculation, and we found only one imaginary frequency, ~ 265 cm^{-1} and ~ 205 cm^{-1} , for pathways I and II, respectively. These results confirm that the highest-energy points are true saddle points of the reaction pathways investigated.

The final results for both pathways are shown in the lower panel of Figure 5 with schematic representations of the molecular geometry at some key points along the reaction pathway. In these figures, the reaction coordinate for the i th image, $\rho^{(i)}$ (with the initial state being the zero image), was calculated using the next expression

Figure 5. Energy along the investigated reaction pathways I and II. The upper panel shows the ANEBA convergence to the MFDP, and in the lower panel we present the final results for the reaction pathways I (left) and II (right). The minimum energy path (MEP) corresponds to pathway II with an activation barrier of 0.52 eV. $-\bullet-$, NEB; $-\oplus-$, level 1; $-\circ-$, level 2; $-\triangle-$, level 3; $-\nabla-$, level 4; $-\star-$, level 5.

$$\rho^{(i)} = \sum_{j=1}^i d(j, j-1) \quad (2)$$

for $i > 0$ ($\rho^{(0)} = 0$), where $d(j, j-1)$ is the distance between images j and $j-1$ defined as follows:

$$d(j, j-1) = \left[\sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{atoms}}} (x_{k,j} - x_{k,j-1})^2 + (y_{k,j} - y_{k,j-1})^2 + (z_{k,j} - z_{k,j-1})^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{r}_{k,j} = (x_{k,j}, y_{k,j}, z_{k,j})$ being the position of the atom k in the image j .

Figure 6 shows the geometrical configuration for the saddle points obtained in pathways I and II. In both cases, the thiolate group remains close to its position in the molecular adsorbed state with the S atom close to a Top position.

It might be argued that spin-unrestricted calculations might be necessary if the SCH₃ and the H atom separate from each other not too close to the surface. We have verified that this is not the case. Spin-unrestricted and spin-restricted calculations for the molecular configuration corresponding to the saddle point of the most favorable reaction pathway give the same results. This is because, when the bond scission takes place, both the H atom and the SCH₃ group are close to the surface.

1. Effect of Surface Relaxation. In general, the effective activation energy barrier for dissociation (with respect to the energy of the reactants) decreases if surface relaxation is taken into account. This might become relevant if the time scale of the H-S dissociation process is similar to or larger than the characteristic time involved in an adsorbate induced surface

Figure 6. Geometrical configuration for the saddle points of pathways I, panel (a); and II, panel (b). In both figures are shown the $d_{\text{H-S}}$ distance.

relaxation process. This might be certainly the case at low surface temperatures for which the mean lifetime of the molecular adsorbed state becomes very long. To investigate the influence of surface relaxation, we have first carried out a full geometry optimization (now including the degrees of freedom of the Au atoms in the two topmost layers) of the initial and final states of the reaction pathways investigated in sections III.A and III.B.

For the molecular adsorbed states, we found that the energy and geometry of adsorption given in section III.A do not change significantly when relaxation of Au atoms is allowed. This is, of course, because molecule-surface interactions are weak in these cases. On the other hand, the energy of the DS is more affected by the surface atom relaxation as a consequence of the stronger chemisorption processes involved. The energy of the DS we have investigated is reduced by ~ 0.19 eV with respect to the values obtained for a frozen substrate. Thus, the dissociation process is exothermic. Only the Au atoms in the neighborhood of the S atom suffer a vertical displacement lower than ~ 0.08 Å without a significant change of the geometry of the adsorbed SCH₃ group ($d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.48$ Å; $d_{\text{H-S}} = 3.75$ Å; and $\alpha_{\text{S-C}} = 56.2^\circ$).

Figure 7. Energy of pathways I and II with (—●—) and without (---○---) surface relaxation as a function of the reaction coordinate. The activation barriers are 0.5 eV for pathway I and 0.4 eV for pathway II, so the reductions of the activation energy due to surface relaxation are 0.06 and 0.1 eV, respectively.

We have carried out NEB and ANEBA calculations allowing relaxation of the coordinates of the molecule and the Au topmost layer atoms, considering the reaction pathways schematized in Figure 4, using the new fully optimized initial and final configurations. We found that the surface atom displacements are small and essentially the molecular geometries are very similar to those shown in Figure 5. As far as geometrical factors are concerned, surface relaxation does not play a crucial role in the present case and the main results obtained for a frozen substrate are preserved. Still, when taking it into account, the obtained value for the minimum activation energy barrier is 0.4 eV (see Figure 7). This result became closer to the value of 0.3 eV estimated from experiments¹ and larger than the that estimated by Sellers.²⁰ This is an encouraging result which provides additional support to the main conclusions of the present work.

IV. Conclusions

In this paper, we have investigated possible reaction pathways for H–SCH₃ bond cleavage on Au(111) at low coverage, through density functional theory calculations. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to explore possible H–SCH₃ dissociation pathways through state-of-the-art electronic structure calculations. We have found a molecular adsorbed state with the S atom located on a Top-Au site and a bonding energy of –0.38 eV, in good agreement with previous calculations and experiments. The energies of reactants and dissociation products are very close to each other, making the reaction exothermic only when adsorbate induced surface relaxation is taken into account.

All the reaction pathways we have investigated present considerable activation energy barriers, with the lowest being 0.52 eV (without surface relaxation). The most favorable dissociation pathways start with the HSCH₃ molecule adsorbed with the S atom on Top, and the lowest activation energy barrier is found for the H atom dissociating toward its nearest Bridge site. The SCH₃ remains very close to its position in the molecular adsorbed state until the H–S distance reaches 2.1 Å at the saddle point of the potential energy surface.

The surface relaxation does not change the main geometrical features of the most favorable dissociation pathway. The Au atom displacements from their equilibrium positions are small but reduce the minimum activation energy barrier to 0.41 eV.

The existence of this high activation energy barrier explains the extremely low reactive sticking probability observed in recent experiments.

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- 1) Love, J.; Estroff, L. A.; Kriebel, J.; Nuzzo, R.; Whitesides, G. *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, *105*, 1103.
- 2) Ulman, A. *Chem. Rev.* **1996**, *96*, 1533.
- 3) Schreiber, F. *Prog. Surf. Sci.* **2000**, *65*, 151.
- 4) Schreiber, F. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2004**, *16*, R881.
- 5) Vericat, C.; Vela, M.; Salvarezza, R. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2005**, *7*, 3258.
- 6) Hohenberg, P.; Kohn, W. *Phys. Rev. B* **1964**, *136*, 864.
- 7) Kohn, W.; Sham, L. J. *Phys. Rev. A* **1965**, *140*, 1133.
- 8) Gronbeck, H.; Curioni, A.; Andreoni, W. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2000**, *122*, 3839.
- 9) Hayashi, T.; Morikawa, Y.; Nozoye, H. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2001**, *114*, 7615.
- 10) Gottschalck, J.; Hammer, B. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2002**, *116*, 784.
- 11) Yourdshahyan, Y.; Rappe, A. J. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2002**, *117*, 825.
- 12) Gonzalez, N.; Lorente, N.; Arnau, A. *Surf. Sci.* **2006**, *600*, 4039–4043.
- 13) Cometto, F.; Paredes-Olivera, P.; Macagno, V.; Patrito, E. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, *109*, 21737.
- 14) Masens, C.; Ford, M. J.; Cortie, M. B. *Surf. Sci.* **2005**, *580*, 19.
- 15) Kondoh, H.; Iwasaki, M.; Shimada, T.; Amemiya, K.; Yokoyama, T.; Otha, T.; Shimomura, M.; Kono, S. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2003**, *90*, 066102.
- 16) Roper, M.; Skegg, M.; Fisher, J.; Lee, J.; Dhanak, V.; Woodruff, D.; Jones, R. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2004**, *389*, 87.
- 17) Maksymovych, P.; Sorescu, D.; Yates, J., Jr. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2006**, *110*, 21161.
- 18) Maksymovych, P.; Sorescu, D.; Dougherty, D.; Yates, J., Jr. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, *109*, 15992.
- 19) Lavrich, D.; Wetterer, S.; Bernasek, S.; Scoles, G. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **1998**, *102*, 3456.
- 20) Sellers, H. *Surf. Sci.* **1993**, *294*, 99.
- 21) Dubois, L.; Zegarski, B.; Nuzzo, R. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 678.
- 22) Rzeznicka, I.; Lee, J.; Maksymovych, P.; Yates, J., Jr. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, *109*, 15992.
- 23) Shustorovich, E. *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **1986**, *6*, 1.
- 24) Shustorovich, E. *Adv. Catal.* **1990**, *37*, 101.
- 25) Payne, M. C.; Teter, M. P.; Allen, D. C.; Joannopoulos, J. D. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **1992**, *64*, 1045.
- 26) Kresse, G.; Hafner, J. *Phys. Rev. B* **1993**, *47*, 558.
- 27) Kresse, G.; Hafner, J. *Phys. Rev. B* **1994**, *49*, 14251.
- 28) Kresse, G.; Furthmüller, J. *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **1996**, *6*, 15.
- 29) Kresse, G.; Furthmüller, J. *Phys. Rev. B* **1996**, *54*, 11169.
- 30) Vanderbilt, D. *Phys. Rev. B* **1990**, *41*, 7892.
- 31) Kresse, G.; Hafner, J. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **1994**, *6*, 8245.

- 32) Perdew, J. P.; Wang, Y. *Phys. Rev. B* **1992**, *45*, 13244.
- 33) Monkhorst, H.; Pack, D. *Phys. Rev. B* **1976**, *13*, 5186.
- 34) Methfessel, M.; Paxton, A. T. *Phys. Rev. B* **1989**, *40*, 3616.
- 35) Lide, D. R., Ed. *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics*, 81st ed.; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, 2001.
- 36) Mills, G.; Jónsson, H. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1994**, *72*, 1124.
- 37) Mills, G.; Jónsson, H.; Schenter, G. K. *Surf. Sci.* **1995**, *324*, 305.
- 38) Jónsson, H.; Mills, G.; Jacobsen, K. W. In *Classical and Quantum Dynamics in Condensed Phase Simulations*; Berne, B. J., Ciccotti, G., Coker, D. F., Eds.; World Scientific: Singapore, 1998.
- 39) Maragakis, P.; Andreev, S.; Brumer, Y.; Reichman, D.; E. Kaxiras, E. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2002**, *117*, 4651.
- 40) Neugebauer, J.; Scheffler, M. *Phys. Rev. B* **1992**, *46*, 16067.
- 41) Makov, G.; Payne, M. C. *Phys. Rev. B* **1995**, *51*, 4014.
- 42) Zhou, J. G.; Hagelberg, F. *Phys. Rev. Lett* **2006**, *97*, 045505.